

1 **HPV E2 activates ZC4H2.**

2 Shahan K. Mamoor, B.S., M.S., Ph.D cand.¹

3 ¹shahanmamoor@gmail.com

4 Chestnut Hill, MA USA 02467

5 East Islip, NY USA 11730

6 HPV E2 is the viral transcriptional activator but likely has a multitude of functions separate from the
7 E1-associated viral trans-activation event that remain undefined. We demonstrate here by ectopic
8 expression of HPV E2 in human cells and measurement of total transcription following next generation
9 RNA-sequencing activation of *Zc4h2* by human papillomavirus E2 protein.

10 Citations

11 1. May, M., Hwang, K.S., Miles, J., Williams, C., Niranjana, T., Kahler, S.G., Chiurazzi, P., Steindl, K.,
12 Van Der Spek, P.J., Swagemakers, S. and Mueller, J., 2015. ZC4H2, an XLID gene, is required for the
13 generation of a specific subset of CNS interneurons. *Human Molecular Genetics*, 24(17), pp.4848-4861.

14 2. Wan, L.P., Li, Y., Zhao, S., Zhao, S., Song, N.N., Yuan, K.M., Yang, C., Ding, Y.Q., Mao, B.,
15 Sheng, N. and Tao, W., 2025. The pathogenic factor of ZC4H2-associated rare disorder is a postsynaptic
16 regulator for synaptic activity and cognitive function. *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences*,
17 122(28), p.e2426375122.

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